

Becoming the Face of the Crisis: A Phenomenological Study of Chief Information Security Officers' Leadership from Breach Detection to Public Disclosure

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Abstract—Cybersecurity leadership research emphasizes technical metrics, yet the personal challenges Chief Information Security Officers (CISOs) face during significant data breaches remain largely unexplored. This descriptive phenomenological study addresses this gap by examining the lived experiences of 16 CISOs as they navigate breach detection, public disclosure, and early recovery. Through in-depth interviews, five essential themes emerged: profound identity transformation from technical experts to *organizational "sense-makers"* and *"governance pivots"*; visceral experience of the "information void" under extreme uncertainty; management of conflicting legal, technical, and reputational imperatives through satisficing rather than optimization; ethical decision-making under conditions designed to compromise integrity; and significant psychological strain functioning as "silent destroyers" of effectiveness. Findings reveal that breach response is fundamentally a multifaceted leadership challenge, requiring ethical stewardship, psychological resilience, and capabilities that extend far beyond technical security expertise. This study establishes the phenomenological foundations for understanding cybersecurity crisis leadership, providing actionable implications for organizational support systems, board education, and regulatory policy.

Index Terms—Information Security Governance, Data Breach Response, Chief Information Security Officer (CISO), Descriptive Phenomenology, Psychological Resilience, Satisficing, Crisis Leadership, Data Security and Governance

1. INTRODUCTION

As cybersecurity threats have intensified, Chief Information Security Officers (CISOs) have faced unprecedented pressures that have fundamentally transformed their leadership roles. Research has identified patterns of burnout and stress among cybersecurity leaders as a consequence. A survey of 3,000 European CISOs found that 82 percent reported feeling burned out, 65 percent believed their positions were set up for failure, and 64 percent had considered quitting their jobs[1]. Interestingly, the same study revealed that CISOs who had experienced data breaches reported lower stress levels (twenty-three percent) than those who had not (forty-seven percent). Managing actual security incidents may mitigate anxieties about hypothetical scenarios. Research on stress and burnout in the

cybersecurity workforce highlights the severity of mental health challenges in this field. A quantitative study of 50 cybersecurity professionals found that 44 percent reported experiencing severe work-related stress and burnout, with 66 percent perceiving their roles as more stressful than those in other IT positions[2]. Nepal et al.[3] conducted a mixed-methods study of 35 incident responders, using digital activity data and self-reported measures. Their analysis revealed that over half of the respondents experienced burnout, which was linked to increased workload, limited control, poor teamwork, and inadequate recognition. Burned-out responders worked more than 40 hours per week, had poor sleep quality, and engaged in more email activities, meetings, and after-hours collaborations. Indeed, the human factors that contribute to cybersecurity stress are well-documented. Nobles [4] argued that security fatigue, stress, and burnout are silent destroyers of cybersecurity effectiveness, noting that business decision-makers often lack the expertise to recognize the negative impacts of these factors. These organizational and psychological pressures intensify dramatically during data breaches, when CISOs must simultaneously manage their own stress while orchestrating complex crisis communications across multiple stakeholder groups. The ability to communicate effectively under such extreme conditions has emerged as one of the most critical—and challenging—competencies for security leaders navigating breach response.

This study contributes to information systems research by addressing calls for greater attention to the human dimensions of cybersecurity [5] [4] and by demonstrating the value of phenomenological inquiry for understanding complex sociotechnical phenomena. By centering the subjective experiences of security leaders, this research complements the technical and organizational perspectives that dominate the information security literature, offering a more comprehensive understanding of how organizations can effectively respond to and recover from cybersecurity crises.

A. Crisis Communication and Stakeholder Management During Breaches

Effective crisis communication has become a critical competency for CISOs managing data breach responses. Jechle et al.[6] examined situational crisis communication theory and found that organizations adopt layered response strategies. They often combine compensation and victimage with apologies, justification, and excuses to acknowledge harm while framing themselves as victims of sophisticated attacks. Another analysis of U.S. breach disclosures identified eighteen different combinations of response strategies, with limited use of denial tactics, suggesting that organizations prioritize maintaining trust and transparency. The timing and quality of crisis communication equally impact stakeholder perceptions and organizational outcomes. Nikkhah and Grover[7] found that stakeholders react to data breaches based on how incidents are communicated, with customers and investors interpreting the same breaches differently. Customers focus on understanding why breaches occurred and whether they could have been prevented, while investors seek additional information through social media beyond official company statements. Shaikh et al.[8] examined 485 U.S. data breach announcements from 2005 to 2018 and found that organizations with stronger security reputations experienced significantly lower financial risk over six months when they disclosed breaches promptly. Similarly, Sapriel[9] studied stakeholder communication during cyber crises, emphasizing that failing to engage stakeholders quickly can escalate crises into reputational disasters. The authors noted that if organizations do not communicate transparently with stakeholders, this lack of communication can severely erode confidence. Recent research has emphasized the importance of timely disclosure, message

consistency, and proactive stakeholder engagement in effective incident management. Tembo[10] conducted a comparative analysis of major cybersecurity incidents and found that structured communication maintained stakeholder trust and facilitated efficient recovery. Conversely, fragmented messaging exacerbated uncertainty and prolonged disruption.

While existing research illuminates organizational strategies and stakeholder responses during security breaches, a critical gap remains: we know remarkably little about how CISOs themselves experience these intense periods of crisis leadership. How do security leaders interpret their transformed roles when they become the public face of organizational failure? What is it like to navigate profound uncertainty while being expected to provide definitive guidance? How do they grapple with the ethical tensions between transparency and caution, or the competing demands of technical containment, legal compliance, and reputation management? These questions are profoundly important because CISOs operate at the intersection of technical expertise, organizational leadership, and public accountability. Yet, their lived experiences during the most consequential moments of their careers remain largely unexplored. This phenomenological study addresses this critical gap by focusing on the perspectives and experiences of CISOs. The research is guided by two primary questions: How do CISOs experience and interpret their roles, decisions, and interactions with internal and external stakeholders in the immediate aftermath of a significant data breach? What tensions, strategies, and supports do CISOs describe when managing uncertainty, ethical considerations, and public accountability from detection through early recovery?

This research establishes a new sociotechnical lens for Information Systems (IS) research by demonstrating that the CISO's role during a crisis is not merely a technical function but an epistemic one. The study introduces the CISO as *chief information synthesis officer*, a leader who manages epistemic ambiguity—the gap between what is known forensically and what is required legally—by acting as a governance pivot. This contributes to a broader understanding of how organizations can effectively navigate the intersection of human interpretation and technical artifacts during cybersecurity crises.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a concise review of prior related studies. Section 3 describes the research design, including the profiles of participants and the data collection procedures, followed by an explanation of the data analysis methods and rigor strategies. Section 4 presents the findings and offers a detailed explanation of the emerging themes. Section 5 discusses the results, theoretical contributions, and implications for practitioners and policymakers. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Phenomenological Approaches in Cybersecurity

Phenomenological approaches have been effectively employed to understand cybersecurity leadership experiences, although such studies remain limited. Caudle[11] conducted a phenomenological study involving 21 senior military officers serving in cyber warfare divisions to explore the uncertainty of decision-making following cyberattacks. The phenomenological reduction analysis revealed that decision-making uncertainty was characterized by five interdependent factors: response process, human factors, governance, technology, and environment. The study recommended policy and strategic changes to enhance senior officers' experiences and situational awareness, as well as to improve collaboration among government departments and agencies. Similarly, a phenomenological

study of IT and cybersecurity professionals in Botswana investigated the perceived effects of leadership on supply chain cybersecurity. This study demonstrates the applicability of phenomenological inquiry to contemporary cybersecurity leadership challenges[12]. In contrast, Zanke et al.[13] employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative interviews with quantitative surveys to assess information security culture within a large international organization. Their work demonstrates how the combination of multiple research methods can yield a more comprehensive understanding of complex security issues. Mbacop et al.[14] examined the implementation of healthcare cybersecurity using a phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of individuals implementing IT security measures. The study employed semi-structured interviews with participants who had a minimum of two years of cybersecurity experience and applied thematic analysis to identify challenges such as resource constraints, compliance burdens, emerging threats, and communication gaps. Similarly, Akter et al.[15] conducted qualitative research using semi-structured interviews with cybersecurity experts across multiple public organizations, employing thematic analysis to reveal three key leadership factors: top management buy-in, resource allocation, and leadership advocacy. Recent qualitative scholarship shows that cybersecurity leadership and threat response are deeply shaped by human and organizational context. For example, Ashenden and Sasse's[16] interview-based study highlights how CISOs' effectiveness can be constrained by organizational culture—especially when credibility, influence, and employee engagement are undermined—suggesting that security work is not purely technical but socially negotiated inside the firm. Complementing that lens, Tawer's[17] phenomenological dissertation captures how data security experts experience modern ransomware as an evolving, high-pressure threat characterized by common entry vectors (e.g., phishing and exposed services), data exfiltration/double extortion, and “living-off-the-land” tactics that force layered, adaptive defenses beyond legacy tools. Taken together, these studies reinforce the value of phenomenological inquiry: understanding cyber incidents requires attention to lived experience—how professionals interpret uncertainty, navigate constraints, and act within cultural and operational pressures that shape real-world response.

B. Ethical Leadership and Decision-Making Under Pressure

Ethical leadership during crises is a critical aspect of a CISO role. Brown et al.[18] define ethical leadership as the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, as well as the promotion of such conduct to followers via two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making. Similarly, Xue et al.[19] examined the relationship between ethical leadership and employee violations of information security policies, arguing that ethical leadership influences security behaviors by encouraging appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships. Kalshoven et al.[20] identified that ethical leadership during crisis response involves fairness in decision-making, transparency, principled and balanced decisions, honesty, responsible actions, and equitable treatment of stakeholders[20] [21]. D'Arcy and Greene[22] concur that leaders who demonstrate ethical behavior foster positive ethical climates, motivating employees to comply with information security practices—an especially critical factor during breach responses when organizational norms are challenged. Research on leadership behaviors and information security policy compliance indicates that behavioral approaches to leadership, which focus on what leaders do and how they act, play a pivotal role in motivating employees to adhere to security controls [23]. Collectively, research on ethical

considerations in organizational conflict reveals that leaders face unique dynamics requiring ethical evaluation to ensure fair, equitable, and ethically sound environments[24]. Consequently, during organizational changes such as responding to data breaches, employees often experience uncertainty about their future roles and job security, which can lead to conflicts arising from fear, resistance, or frustration.

C. Regulatory Compliance and Legal Pressures

CISOs must navigate complex and constantly evolving regulatory requirements during breach response. Pavan[25] examined how organizations manage changing data protection laws to mitigate security risks. Major regulatory frameworks, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), impose stringent data protection standards that significantly influence how organizations notify stakeholders and respond to data breaches. The complexity of complying with cross-border regulatory requirements presents particular challenges. Today's regulatory environment presents significant challenges for global organizations, which must address the growing risk of data breaches. Compliance with multiple international breach notification laws requires a thorough understanding of the conditions that trigger statutorily mandated notice obligations, as well as the procedures for and recipients of such notices[26].

Furthermore, definitions of data breaches vary significantly across jurisdictions. Singapore broadly defines a data breach as "access, collection, use, disclosure, copying, modification, or disposal of personal data." In contrast, some U.S. states require that unauthorized access compromise the security, confidentiality, or integrity of protected information. Recently, the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) expanded data breach notification rules, requiring covered entities to notify customers without unreasonable delay and within thirty days after a reasonable determination of a breach[27]. The expanded definition of "breach" includes any unauthorized access to, use of, or disclosure of covered data, as well as any disclosure that exceeds authorized access. It addresses both malicious activities and inadvertent unauthorized access. Similarly, the Federal Trade Commission has implemented new breach notification requirements under the Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act Safeguards Rule, which mandates that financial institutions report breaches affecting 500 or more individuals[28]. This provision highlights the risks of both under-reporting and over-reporting breaches, which create additional decision-making pressures. Organizations that fail to meet notification requirements face substantial fines and penalties, while over-reporting can lead to regulatory scrutiny and raise questions about their organizational competence[29].

D. Organizational Response Strategies and Human Factors

Research on organizational response strategies highlights the importance of preparation and systematic approaches to breach response, as complete prevention is practically infeasible[30]. The immediate post-breach period demands exceptional leadership. The first 48 to 72 hours following a data breach are critical, requiring decisions to be made quickly yet deliberately, as they balance the technical imperatives of containment with business needs for continuity[31]. This period requires a careful balance between transparency and discretion, particularly regarding regulatory requirements that vary across jurisdictions.

The effectiveness of post-breach management has a significant impact on long-term organizational outcomes. Research indicates that greater information security legitimacy, demonstrated through proactive security

enhancements and effective post-breach management, reduces firm-specific risk by signaling a lower likelihood of future breaches and stronger security governance[8]. Human factors play a crucial role in understanding the experiences of CISOs during breaches. Studies on human factors in cybersecurity leadership reveal that unintentional issues, such as lack of knowledge, skill deficits, negligence, and misinformation, can facilitate cyber threats[5]. Additionally, leadership integrity and its impact on moral decision-making constitute another vital dimension; leaders who embody integrity are better equipped to navigate challenges and crises effectively[32] [33].

E. Gaps in the Literature

Despite growing research on cybersecurity leadership, significant gaps remain in understanding the lived experiences of CISOs during breach response. Existing studies predominantly focus on the technical aspects of incident response, organizational outcomes, or employee behaviors, with limited attention to the phenomenological experiences of security leaders during crisis periods[12] [33]. The available literature lacks a comprehensive examination of how CISOs perceive and interpret their roles during breaches, particularly regarding their interactions with diverse stakeholder groups and navigating ethical tensions under public scrutiny[34]. This phenomenological study addresses these gaps by centering on CISO perspectives and experiences, exploring the essence of what it means to lead security response during organizational crises.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive phenomenological approach to understand the lived experiences of CISOs during a significant, reportable data breach, from detection through public disclosure and early recovery. A breach is not merely a technical incident but also a critical security issue. It represents a leadership crisis characterized by ambiguity, rapid decision-making, and competing demands from legal counsel, executives and boards, communications teams, regulators, customers, and the media. Phenomenological inquiry is particularly appropriate because it focuses on how individuals perceive, interpret, and make meaning of an experience, aiming to describe the shared essence across participants [35] [36]. Rather than testing variables or developing a process theory, this design remains closely aligned with participants' accounts of pressure, ethical tension, and public accountability. Data will be collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews that invite CISOs to recount specific moments, decisions, and interactions. Analysis will follow established phenomenological procedures, including bracketing to surface the researcher's assumptions, horizontalization to identify significant statements, clustering into meaning units, and the development of textural and structural descriptions that culminate in a composite essence[37] [36]. This approach provides the depth necessary to illuminate what breach leadership feels like, not just the actions taken in real time. This study employs descriptive phenomenology to explore the essence of CISOs' experiences during breach response, focusing on understanding what these experiences meant to those who lived them.

A. Research Questions

This study was guided by two primary research questions: (1) How do CISOs experience and interpret their roles, decisions, and interactions with internal and external stakeholders during the immediate aftermath of a significant data breach? (2) What tensions, strategies, and supports do CISOs describe when managing uncertainty,

ethical considerations, and public accountability from detection through early recovery? As shown in Table I, twelve semi-structured interview questions were developed to elicit rich phenomenological data regarding the lived experiences of CISOs during data breach response, aligning with the research questions and the thematic context established by the literature review.

B. Participants and Data Collection

As a fundamental requirement of phenomenology, the phenomenon under investigation must be experienced by the participants[37]. This study was conducted through semi-structured interviews with participants who met specific inclusion criteria. Participants were required to currently serve, or have served within the last three to five years, as the CISO or an equivalent top information security leader for an organization in the U.S. or Canada. Additionally, participants must have led the response to at least one publicly disclosed data breach that necessitated legal or regulatory notification. Direct involvement in post-breach communications with executives, board members, and at least one external group, such as the media, regulators, customers, or partners, was required. Finally, participants needed to be willing to discuss their experiences without disclosing confidential technical details or violating non-disclosure agreements. To identify primary participants, purposive sampling, a type of non-probability sampling, was employed. Snowball sampling was then used to recruit additional participants; this method expands the sample by asking one participant to recommend others for interviews[35]. Using this sampling strategy, sixteen participants who met the above criteria were selected for the study. The sample included twelve men and four women, aged between 30 and 55 years. Based on data triangulation, participants were drawn from diverse industries, including healthcare (n = 7), financial services (n = 4), insurance (n = 3), and utilities (n = 2). As shown in Table II, participants had varied experience, ranging from two to sixteen years in security leadership roles, with educational backgrounds comprising bachelor's degrees (n = 3), master's degrees (n = 12), and doctoral degrees (n = 1). Primary data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews, which lasted 60 to 90 minutes and were conducted via secure video conferencing. The interviews focused on specific moments from detection to disclosure and early recovery. All sessions were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim for analysis and review.

C. Thematic Analysis and Rigor

All interviews were analyzed using phenomenological procedures, including horizontalization, identification of meaning units, and the development of textural and structural descriptions, culminating in composite essence descriptions[36]. The analytical process began after participants had the opportunity to review their transcripts and provide edits. Transcripts were read multiple times to gain an overall understanding of the data. Interview transcripts were initially coded by identifying unique and salient statements and compiling lists of them. The coding process continued by pinpointing text passages focused on meanings within the research context or potentially meaningful to external audiences. These text segments varied in length, typically consisting of one or two sentences. The transcripts were then analyzed to identify emerging themes. No predetermined codes were used during the interviews, as employing prior codes may hinder analysis and the development of new ideas[38]. Initially, significant codes were identified through transcript analysis, leading to the development of concepts, sub-themes, and themes. Themes were named through abstraction, reflecting the most salient features within participants' words.

The next stage involved clustering existing themes in a logically meaningful way by exploring the relationships among them. Subsequently, each theme was elaborated upon narratively based on participants' words. Analysis of transcripts and memos continued until no new patterns emerged, indicating that saturation had been reached.

Analytic rigor was ensured through multiple strategies that enhanced credibility and confirmed validity. An audit trail documented all analytical decisions and processes. Reflexive memos were maintained throughout data collection and analysis to bracket the researcher’s assumptions and preconceptions. Maximum-variation sampling across industries, experience levels, and organizational contexts improved the transferability of the findings. Member checking was employed by allowing participants to review the results and interpretations, inviting them to make corrections as needed to confirm the meanings and interpretations assigned to their interviews[35]. These rigorous strategies ensured the trustworthiness of the results and prevented the investigation of phenomena based solely on the researchers’ preconceived beliefs.

TABLE I SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

S/N	Semi-structured Interview Questions
1	Could you walk me through a significant, reportable breach you led, starting from the moment it was detected, through public disclosure, and into the early recovery period?
2	In the first hours or days after detection, what stood out most to you about what was happening, and how did you interpret your role in that moment?
3	During that period, how did you experience being (or perceived as) the face of the incident, and what did that role mean to you both personally and professionally?
4	What were the most consequential decisions you made from detection through disclosure, and how did you determine what to prioritize when information was incomplete or evolving?
5	How did you manage uncertainty - such as technical unknowns, attribution questions, and scope ambiguity - while still providing direction and reassurance to others?
6	Describe your interactions with internal stakeholders - including executives, the board, legal, communications, and risk/compliance teams - during the immediate aftermath. What aspects were supportive, and what challenges did you encounter?
7	What tensions did you experience while balancing technical containment with legal risks, reputational concerns, and operational continuity? Can you share an instance when these demands conflicted with one another?
8	Were there instances where ethical considerations influenced or challenged your decisions (e.g., transparency versus caution, speed versus accuracy, customer impact versus organizational risk)? What actions did you take, and how did you feel about them?
9	What was your experience preparing for and navigating public disclosure (including notifications, statements, and briefings)? How did the concept of “accountability” manifest for you during that phase?
10	How did you engage with external stakeholders—such as regulators, customers, partners, and the media—and what challenges did you encounter during those interactions?
11	What strategies did you use to maintain effectiveness under intense pressure, such as communication approaches, decision-making routines, delegation, and personal coping practices? Which of these helped you the most in the moment?
12	Looking back, which supports—such as people, structures, playbooks, culture, and prior experiences—mattered most? What would you want other CISOs or organizations to understand about the lived reality of this period?

IV. FINDINGS

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of 16 CISOs who managed significant, reportable data breaches from detection through public disclosure and early recovery. Participants represented sectors including healthcare, financial services, insurance, and utilities, with experience ranging from 2 to over 16 years in security leadership roles. Through in-depth, semi-structured interviews, five essential themes, as shown in Figure I, emerged that illuminate the core phenomenological essence of leading organizational breach response amid profound uncertainty, competing demands, and intense public scrutiny.

A. Theme 1: Role Transformation and the Experience of Becoming "The Face"

1) From Technical Expert to Organizational Sensemaker

The most striking finding across all participants was the immediate and profound transformation in how CISOs experienced their professional identity during breach response. Rather than functioning primarily as technical security leaders, participants described perceiving their roles through fundamentally different lenses during crisis periods. Participant 4 (P4), an experienced healthcare leader, vividly captured this transformation: "I shifted from technical leader to *Chief Information Synthesis Officer*, sifting noise from facts while translating complex findings for the executive team." This sense of becoming an information translator and sense-maker emerged consistently across interviews. The metaphors participants used revealed the embodied nature of this transformation. They described themselves as "traffic controllers," ensuring that technical containment did not violate legal hold requirements while preserving business continuity. Similarly, participant 16 (P16), with 13 years of experience in the utilities sector, described becoming a "governance pivot" managing response processes, technology, and governance factors simultaneously in high-stakes environments. Some described their transformed identity as "*compliance guarantors*," ensuring every action remained auditable and strictly adhered to regulatory statutes. These metaphorical self-descriptions illuminate how CISOs experienced a fundamental shift from technical problem-solving to orchestrating complex organizational responses under conditions of intense uncertainty.

2) Public Accountability as a Professional Vulnerability

Being the public face of organizational failure emerged as one of the most psychologically demanding aspects of the experience. Participants described this visibility using language that conveyed vulnerability, judgment, and existential professional threats. Participant 9 (P9), who has over a decade of experience in the financial services sector, described it as "holding a mirror up to the entire organization's security posture," an experience that was "personally isolating yet "the ultimate test of leadership integrity." Another participant found it "terrifying," with an acute awareness that "any hesitation or fragmented messaging could exacerbate uncertainty and prolong the disruption." Indeed, the experience of public accountability carried different meanings across sectors. For a utilities leader, being the face meant "the ultimate burden of responsibility for public safety," with accountability shifting "from financial risk to existential risk" due to the critical infrastructure implications. An insurance leader experienced it as "a public trial of our entire security governance structure." However, several participants described how prior experiences tempered these intense feelings. One noted that previous breach experiences "helped temper the anxiety about the hypothetical scenario," viewing visibility as "an opportunity to demonstrate structured

communication." For others, the experience "contributed significantly to burnout," as "public scrutiny combined with intense workload made the job feel set up for failure."

3) Ethical Identity Under Pressure

Participants often experienced their roles through ethical and moral dimensions, relating to concepts such as integrity, fairness, and responsibility. A novel finding of this study is the emergence of a sector-specific hierarchy of values that guides ethical decision-making during a crisis. While standard security logic prioritizes data containment, participants in the healthcare sector ($n = 7$) consistently prioritized "patient safety and operational continuity" over technical containment protocols. For example, P6 faced the decision of whether to follow a containment protocol or pay a ransom to restore operations; they ultimately prioritized life-safety, demonstrating that the healthcare CISO's ethical identity is fundamentally tethered to the clinical mission rather than just technical defense. This distinction suggests that "integrity" for a CISO is not a universal technical standard but is defined by the primary service of the organization. This ethical dimension was most acutely tested when participants felt pressured to compromise transparency or accuracy. One financial services executive described an "ethical conflict" when the CEO pushed for under-reporting to avoid regulatory scrutiny. Similarly, a utilities participant felt "ethically obligated to confirm the broadest possible impact to regulators despite pressure to minimize the scope for "reputational protection". These moments forced leaders to navigate the tension between organizational self-interest and professional integrity, experiencing their roles as guardians of ethical conduct under conditions that incentivized compromise.

B. Theme 2: Navigating the "Information Void"

1) Uncertainty as a Lived Experience

Perhaps the most universally challenging aspect of their experience was managing extreme uncertainty while being expected to provide definitive guidance to stakeholders. Participants described this uncertainty not as an abstract challenge but as a lived, visceral experience that shaped every interaction and decision. One participant characterized the experience by saying, "the information deficit was deafening," capturing the sense of disorientation during the early hours when crucial facts remained unknown. Another leader spent "two weeks trying to definitively prove if data was exfiltrated," with "ambiguity around data loss prolonging the disclosure timeline." This temporal dimension, marked by prolonged, anxious waiting for confirmation, was deeply distressing. Overall, participants described various strategies for managing uncertainty; however, these accounts revealed that uncertainty was never truly "managed" but instead endured and navigated. Participant 1 (P1) relied on "being obsessively transparent about what we knew versus what we did not," and established a "response process framework" to address uncertainty through governance and human factors controls. P4 took a different approach, "communicating uncertainty as a known variable, normalizing the incomplete information flow," and reassuring stakeholders that "uncertainty was built into the process."

2) Process as a Psychological Anchor

Beyond operational utility, participants utilized procedural frameworks as psychological anchors to manage visceral disorientation. One healthcare leader (P7) noted that when technical facts were unknown, the "next three technical steps" provided the emotional regulation necessary to keep the team grounded. This reveals that in IS crisis management, playbooks serve a dual function: they are both technical artifacts and tools for emotional regulation. These approaches reflect a phenomenological reality in which certainty about process compensates for uncertainty about facts.

3) The 48 to 72-Hour Crucible

Multiple participants identified the first 48 to 72 hours as a distinct phenomenological period characterized by compressed time, high-stakes decisions, and intense cognitive demands. One described this as "the clock ticking against the 48 to 72-hour window of critical decision-making," requiring "highly specific, technical instructions to incident response teams." Another emphasized an "extreme focus on the first 48 to 72 hours, knowing that quick, deliberate decisions separate exceptional leaders." The experience of time during this period appeared fundamentally different—simultaneously racing forward while individual moments stretched with significance. One participant described a compressed timeline where "prioritization shifted every 30 minutes," necessitating rapid decision-making under conditions of incomplete information.

C. Theme 3: The Multi-Directional Pull of Competing Demands

1) Legal versus Technical Imperatives

A central aspect of their experience was being pulled simultaneously in multiple directions by competing organizational imperatives. The relationship between legal requirements and technical necessities proved particularly challenging. Participant 3 (P3), a healthcare leader, described a situation in which "technical containment meant potentially deleting logs needed for legal discovery," resulting in hours of delay "while legal provided clearance, prioritizing legal hold over pure containment speed." A financial services participant encountered conflict when the "forensic depth required to definitively prove exfiltration threatened to delay notification past the strict 30-day regulatory window," ultimately prioritizing the notification deadline. Another participant faced ongoing tension when needing "to cut off access to a key data stream, which severely impacted trading but was essential for containment." These tensions were managed through compromise rather than optimization. The findings demonstrate that CISOs do not "optimize" their response but rather engage in "satisficing under scrutiny". This is a distinct leadership competency where the CISO makes defensible compromises—such as delaying technical containment to preserve legal logs—knowing these decisions will be justified later to conflicting stakeholder groups. Success in this context is defined by workable, constrained decision-making rather than idealized technical perfection.

2) Reputation versus Transparency

The tension between protecting organizational reputation and maintaining transparency emerged as both a practical challenge and an ethical dilemma. One participant recounted that "PR wanted us to frame the incident as a 'victim crisis,' while forensics identified clear, preventable missteps," ultimately choosing not to use denial strategies

to maintain transparency. Participant 2 (P2) experienced pressure from the legal team to "minimize the scope of the breach to reduce reputational damage." However, he felt "ethically obligated to confirm the broadest possible impact to regulators," opting for transparency despite organizational pressure to exercise caution. Several participants described facing pressure to downplay the breach's scope or delay disclosure for reputational reasons, yet they felt compelled to prioritize transparency despite these pressures from their organization.

3) **Cross-Jurisdictional Complexity**

For security leaders operating globally, the competing demands of various regulatory regimes create additional complexity. One breach involved "a denial-of-service attack coupled with data theft from our European subsidiary", resulting in immediate challenges related to GDPR and local compliance. This required understanding how specific facts trigger multiple international notification laws. Another case involved "managing different notification triggers," with tension between "notifying jurisdiction A promptly and waiting until complete data was available for jurisdiction B," ultimately prioritizing "consistent messaging worldwide". This finding highlights how geographic complexity amplifies the competing demands that CISOs must navigate.

D. Theme 4: Ethical Decision-Making and Psychological Strain

1) **Transparency as a Moral Commitment**

The tension between transparency and caution emerged as a significant ethical challenge for CISOs, reflecting their professional values. P1 described this "ethical test" as a conflict between "transparency versus caution," ultimately deciding to "issue a broad notice and commit to follow-up, ensuring fairness and honesty." Another participant resisted "pressure to rush the attribution finding, knowing that an incorrect attribution would destroy trust," standing by "the principled decision to prioritize truth over expediency." These accounts reveal transparency not merely as a policy but as a moral commitment tested under conditions designed to undermine it. Participants faced difficult ethical decisions regarding the attribution of blame. For example, participant 5 (P5), a healthcare executive, grappled with whether to "inform patients that the breach was due to a specific internal individual's negligence or to frame it as a systemic failure," ultimately choosing the latter "to protect the individual while emphasizing policy change." This illustrates the ethical complexity in which competing values—transparency, individual protection, and systemic learning—could not be simultaneously maximized.

2) **The Human Cost**

The psychological and emotional toll of breach response emerged as a significant yet often overlooked aspect of their experience. While most participants initially focused on technical and organizational challenges, several directly addressed the human cost of serving as breach response leaders. Participant 6 (P6), with over nine years of experience in the healthcare sector, uniquely emphasized "the human element," managing "the immediate, severe stress and psychological strain within my team". While also feeling personally responsible, P6 recognized that the role "was equally about being a resilience leader and a technical responder, promoting mental health support alongside forensic analysis." The most compelling finding was the organizational imperative to "prioritize support systems to maintain the well-being and ethical grounding of security leaders," underscoring the reality that "the lived

experience involves severe stress and burnout." An intriguing paradox emerged: one crisis veteran noted that prior experiences "helped temper the anxiety about the hypothetical scenario," while another, facing their first major breach, found that "the hypothetical stress I had anticipated was less severe than the actual response." However, the cumulative toll across multiple incidents may increase vulnerability to burnout over the course of a career.

3) The Consequential Decisions That Defined the Response

Participants identified specific pivotal decisions that fundamentally shaped their breach response trajectories. These were not routine tactical choices but rather moments that required balancing competing organizational imperatives with incomplete information under severe time pressure. For example, P1 decided to prioritize "forensic depth over speed of disclosure," choosing "accuracy over hitting the earliest notification window, believing that long-term trust required complete information." In contrast, participant 8 (P8), a financial services executive, faced opposite pressures and prioritized "the notification deadline (legal risk) and committing to follow-up disclosures" when forensic depth threatened regulatory timelines. Although consequential, these types of decisions are sometimes made with limited or incomplete information. P6 confronted the highly consequential decision of "whether to pay the ransom to restore critical operations (a business continuity decision) versus following protocol (a containment decision)." The leader ultimately prioritized "patient safety and operational continuity first." This finding reveals how healthcare sector contexts elevate certain values, such as patient safety, above standard security protocols.

E. Theme 5: Stakeholder Communication and Organizational Readiness

1) Divergent Stakeholder Expectations

Engaging external stakeholders presented distinct challenges, as different groups required fundamentally different communication approaches and held varying expectations. Interactions with regulators were universally demanding. One participant described HIPAA regulators as "the most challenging; their requirements were extensive and demanded immediate, precise data, contrasting sharply with the media's demand for simple soundbites." Sector-specific regulatory regimes created unique communication challenges that required specialized technical translations. Another notable finding was that customers and investors reacted differently based on their distinct concerns. One observed, "Customers and investors reacted differently. Investors focused on social media for information, while customers concentrated on the locus of causality. This required two distinct communication strategies." These differing expectations demonstrate that effective external communication depends on understanding what each stakeholder wants and how they interpret information.

2) The Foundation of Preparation

Security leaders who invested in preparation before breaches experienced markedly different response dynamics. The quality of pre-existing structures emerged as the most critical factor distinguishing manageable responses from chaotic ones. One financial services leader noted, "The playbook was invaluable, particularly the pre-approved legal language for notification." These structures reduced cognitive load by transforming complex decisions into procedural steps. Organizational culture—especially ethics and integrity—proved essential. Another

participant observed that "a culture that already nurtured integrity leadership was essential for ethical decision-making during the crisis." The board's understanding of cybersecurity risk proved to be critical support. Participant P10, an experienced financial services leader, benefited from 'the board's understanding that complete prevention is practically infeasible.' This support fostered psychological safety, enabling individuals to focus on responding rather than assigning blame.

3) Accountability in Transition

The experience of public disclosure marked a significant shift in the phenomenology of the breach experience. Participant 12 (P12), an insurance executive with over a decade of experience, described accountability as "the ultimate loss of control," noting that "despite months of preparation, public scrutiny stripped away professional distance." Another participant likened it to "jumping off a cliff," explaining that "accountability felt like facing the consequences of our past preventative decisions." In regulated industries, accountability took on additional dimensions. One seasoned professional described it as "an audit in real-time," where accountability was defined by ensuring zero errors in regulatory filings.

Altogether, these findings shed light on the phenomenological essence of serving as the Chief Information Security Officer during breach response. A profound transformation of identity characterizes the experience. From technical expert to organizational sense-maker—navigating the "information void" amid intense uncertainty. At the same time, managing competing organizational imperatives that pull simultaneously in multiple directions, making complex ethical decisions under extreme pressure with a serious psychological toll, and engaging in sophisticated stakeholder communication across diverse constituencies. Therefore, preparation, frameworks, and organizational culture established prior to breaches are critical determinants of response effectiveness. At the same time, the personal and team psychological costs represent an underappreciated dimension that requires urgent attention within organizations. Breach response is fundamentally a leadership challenge that demands capabilities extending far beyond technical security expertise. It encompasses strategic communication, ethical decision-making, stakeholder management, and the cultivation of organizational resilience. The discussion section will situate these findings within the existing literature.

TABLE II PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE

Participants	Gender	Age	Sector	Highest Degree	Years of Experience
P1	Male	45 - 50	Healthcare	Master's Degree	12
P2	Female	35 - 40	Healthcare	Master's Degree	5
P3	Male	30 - 35	Healthcare	Bachelor's Degree	2
P4	Male	50 - 55	Healthcare	Master's Degree	15
P5	Male	50 - 55	Healthcare	PhD	12
P6	Male	40 - 45	Healthcare	Bachelor's Degree	9
P7	Female	40 - 45	Healthcare	Master's Degree	7
P8	Male	45 - 50	Financial Services	Master's Degree	6
P9	Male	45 - 50	Financial Services	Master's Degree	10
P10	Male	35 - 40	Financial Services	Master's Degree	6
P11	Female	40 - 45	Financial Services	Master's Degree	8

P12	Male	45 - 50	Insurance	Master's Degree	11
P13	Female	40 - 45	Insurance	Master's Degree	7
P14	Male	35 - 40	Insurance	Master's Degree	4
P15	Male	50 - 55	Utilities	Master's Degree	16
P16	Male	50 - 55	Utilities	Master's Degree	13

Fig. 1. Thematic Structure Diagram Showing the Five Essential Themes of CISOs Lived Experience During Breach Response

V. DISCUSSION

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of 16 Chief Information Security Officers during the critical period from breach detection through public disclosure and early recovery. The findings reveal a complex interplay of role transformation, uncertainty navigation, competing organizational demands, ethical decision-making, psychological strain, and stakeholder communication challenges that fundamentally characterize the CISO experience during organizational crises. This discussion situates these findings within the existing literature, identifies theoretical contributions, and articulates implications for practitioners and policymakers.

A. Role Transformation and Leadership Identity

The finding that CISOs undergo profound role transformation during breach response—shifting from technical experts to *organizational sense-makers*, “*traffic controllers, governance pivots, and compliance guarantors*”—extends existing cybersecurity leadership research. While Caudle[11] describes decision-making uncertainty through response processes, governance, and environmental factors, this study reveals how leaders experience these influences through metaphorical identity shifts that reshape professional self-perception.

The lived experience of becoming “the face” of organizational failure represents an under-examined dimension of cybersecurity leadership. CISOs perceive their roles through ethical dimensions as “guardians of ethical conduct,” aligning with Brown et al.’s[18] conceptualization of ethical leadership through normatively appropriate conduct. However, this study exposes the intense psychological burden of maintaining integrity under conditions designed to compromise it, extending Xue et al.’s[19] work into crisis contexts where organizational self-interest directly conflicts with professional values.

Experienced CISOs reported reduced fear of hypothetical scenarios after actual breach events, yet repeated incidents accumulated into burnout risk. This partially aligns with SecurityWeek’s[1] finding of lower stress among CISOs who experienced breaches (23%) versus those who had not (47%), but reveals greater complexity: crisis-related stress may diminish short-term while long-term burnout risk increases—a nuance quantitative surveys cannot capture.

B. Uncertainty, Time, and the Information Void

Characterizing uncertainty as a “lived, visceral experience” rather than abstract cognitive challenge offers new phenomenological insight. CISOs found psychological stability through procedural certainties—knowing “the next three technical steps” even when attribution remained unknown. This extends Caudle’s[11] work by demonstrating how adherence to process functions as emotional regulation strategy, revealing that IS crisis management playbooks serve dual functions: technical artifacts and psychological anchors.

The identification of the first 48-72 hours as a distinct phenomenological period—characterized by compressed time and high-stakes decisions—empirically validates practitioner assertions about this critical window[31]. The subjective experience of time proved paradoxical: simultaneously racing forward while individual moments stretched with significance. This temporal distortion reveals previously undocumented dimensions of crisis

leadership, suggesting effective response requires not only rapid decision-making but capacity to manage dynamic experiences of temporality itself.

C. Competing Demands and Stakeholder Communication

CISOs experience competing organizational demands as embodied conflicts resolved through compromise rather than optimization. While Nikkhah and Grover[7] found customers and investors respond differently to breaches, this study reveals what managing these competing reactions simultaneously feels like under time pressure with incomplete information. The practical need for "two distinct communication strategies" exemplifies stakeholder-specific interpretive frameworks in action.

Tension between legal requirements and technical imperatives—such as when containment necessitates deleting logs required for legal discovery—represents previously under-explored breach response complexity. While regulatory compliance research addresses requirements[27][28], this study reveals how security leaders personally navigate conflicting demands during time-sensitive responses through satisficing rather than optimization.

Cross-jurisdictional complexity amplifies these tensions. One case involving European subsidiary data theft created immediate GDPR challenges requiring understanding of how specific facts trigger multiple international notification obligations. Another involved managing different notification triggers with tension between prompt notification for jurisdiction A versus waiting for complete data for jurisdiction B, ultimately prioritizing consistent worldwide messaging. These findings illuminate how geographic complexity multiplies the competing demands CISOs must navigate.

D. Ethical Decision-Making and Its Psychological Costs

Transparency as "moral commitment tested under conditions designed to compromise it" significantly contributes to understanding ethical crisis leadership. While Kalshoven et al.[20][21] identified fairness and principled decision-making as ethical leadership characteristics, this study reveals how these principles face active organizational pressure for expedience or reputation protection. The moral complexity of balancing transparency, individual security, and systemic learning—such as deciding whether to disclose individual negligence or frame breaches as systemic failures—represents previously unexplored ethical terrain.

Stress and fatigue as "silent destroyers" of effectiveness validates and extends existing cybersecurity burnout research[2][3][4][34]. This study advances literature by demonstrating psychological strain intensifies acutely during breach crises rather than manifesting solely as chronic occupational stress. One participant explicitly prioritized "mental health support alongside forensic analysis," framing the role as "equally about *resilience leadership* and technical response." This dual imperative challenges techno-rational breach management models and signals fundamental reconceptualization of CISO competencies beyond traditional technical expertise.

The organizational mandate to "prioritize support systems to maintain well-being and ethical grounding of security leaders" exposes critical deficiency: current organizational responses inadequately address cybersecurity workforce mental health. While Nepal et al.[3] established that digital detox interventions and mental health supports effectively mitigate cybersecurity fatigue, this study reveals troubling implementation gap—such supports remain conspicuously absent during breach responses precisely when cognitive and emotional demands peak. This

disconnect between evidence-based recommendations and organizational practice represents systemic failure to protect psychological welfare of security leaders at their most vulnerable juncture.

E. Preparation, Culture, and Organizational Readiness

The study found that pre-existing structures, such as playbooks containing "pre-approved legal language for notification," were "perhaps the single most important factor distinguishing manageable responses from chaotic ones." Additionally, these structures reduced cognitive load by clarifying actions and converting complex decisions into procedural steps. The study found self-detection signaled strong internal security and helped reduce the perceived risk to the firm. This finding supports Shaikh et al.[8] in their examination of information security legitimacy and firm-specific risk. At the same time, our phenomenological data adds nuance to the discussion: CISOs experienced self-detection as both a painful admission of failure and proof that the organization's defenses were effective.

F. Theoretical Contributions

This study advances the theory of cybersecurity leadership and crisis management in several significant ways. First, it provides a phenomenological foundation for understanding the actual experiences of CISOs during breach response. The findings reveal that crisis leadership involves more than just technical skills or decision-making frameworks; it is also deeply personal. CISOs reported identity shifts and sustained psychological strain, experiences that can fundamentally reshape their professional self-perception. This perspective addresses a gap in the existing literature, which often emphasizes organizational outcomes, technical response procedures, or survey-based measures of stress. By employing a phenomenological approach, this study highlights the human dimension of leadership, illustrating what it truly feels like to lead during a breach.

Second, the study reveals that effective breach response requires capabilities extending far beyond technical security expertise to encompass what might be termed crisis leadership competencies. Capabilities include tolerance for uncertainty, ethical decision-making under pressure, effective communication with diverse stakeholders across various interpretive frameworks, and psychological resilience. The study challenges the narrow, technical definitions of CISO competency prevalent in both academic literature and professional practice. Simultaneously, this suggests reconceptualizing cybersecurity leadership as a fundamentally multidimensional phenomenon.

Third, the study shows that CISOs often manage competing demands by compromising rather than attempting to "optimize" every decision. In a breach, there is rarely a perfect choice. Technical urgency clashes with legal risk, reputational fallout, and operational pressure. Consequently, leaders satisfice by making decisions that are good enough, defensible, and workable in the moment. This insight is important because it suggests that the effectiveness of breach response should not be measured against idealized standards of optimal decision-making. Instead, it should be assessed using frameworks that recognize satisficing as a realistic and responsible strategy in the face of unavoidable tensions. This finding reframes how organizations define and measure "success" in breach response.

Fourth, this study contributes to ethical leadership theory by revealing how ethical principles are challenged during organizational crises. It extends existing conceptualizations of ethical leadership from stable organizational contexts to crisis periods, when pressures to compromise are most intense. The finding that some CISOs maintained

their ethical commitments despite organizational pressure, while others compromised, suggests that individual and organizational factors moderating the effectiveness of ethical leadership during crises warrant further investigation.

Fifth, this study advances IS theory by introducing the concept of *satisficing under scrutiny*. Unlike routine organizational decision-making, the CISO must make rapid, high-stakes compromises while simultaneously managing the "Face of Failure". This challenges the techno-rational paradigm in IS research, suggesting that effectiveness should be measured by the ability to manage epistemic ambiguity under accountability rather than just technical metrics.

G. Implications for Information Systems Research

This study challenges the techno-rational paradigm dominating information systems (IS) security leadership research. First, the findings reveal that effective crisis response depends less on optimizing technical solutions and more on managing "epistemic ambiguity under accountability", making defensible decisions with incomplete information while facing intense scrutiny from audiences with conflicting expectations. Future IS research might productively explore how security leaders develop tolerance for ambiguity, manage identity threats during organizational crises, and navigate the emotional demands of serving as "*organizational sense-makers*" rather than purely technical problem-solvers. This shift has broader implications for how IS scholarship conceptualizes leadership in other high-stakes, high-uncertainty contexts such as digital transformation initiatives, system failures, and algorithmic accountability crises.

Secondly, this study demonstrates that breach response is fundamentally sociotechnical, requiring integration of human, organizational, and technical dimensions. CISOs utilize procedural frameworks as "psychological anchors," demonstrating that protocols serve dual functions; they are both technical artifacts and emotional regulation tools. Future research should treat psychological factors as first-order variables rather than peripheral concerns. The identification of "silent destroyers" (stress and fatigue) reveals that a CISO's technical capacity is inextricably linked to their psychological resilience. We propose an integrative framework that models the interdependencies between technical response, emotional regulation via protocols, and stakeholder-specific interpretive frameworks.

H. Implications for Practitioners and Policymakers

Taken together, these findings have significant implications for both practitioners and policymakers. For organizations, the recruitment, development, and support of CISOs should emphasize not only technical expertise but also crisis leadership competencies. This includes communication skills, ethical decision-making, stakeholder management, and psychological resilience. Organizations should prepare technical playbooks and pre-approved communication templates in advance to ensure effective communication. Additionally, they should establish clear escalation protocols and stakeholder notification procedures to minimize cognitive load during high-stress situations. Interestingly, the study reveals that stress and fatigue can become "silent destroyers" during breach response. When left unmanaged, performance declines—often unnoticed until it is too late. Therefore, organizations should consider support systems an integral part of incident response rather than optional add-ons. This includes providing mental health resources, implementing team rotation and recovery periods, and encouraging boundaries, such as brief

digital detoxes when feasible. For practitioners, the role must transition to "*resilience leadership*," where mental health support is integrated into the incident response (IR) playbook alongside forensics. While technical execution remains crucial, pushing teams to maximize output without addressing psychological strain can have unintended consequences. It undermines the quality of decision-making and communication precisely when they need to be at their strongest. For boards and executives, the findings underscore the need for more realistic expectations regarding both the likelihood of breaches and the complexity of responses to them. Several CISOs noted a beneficial shift when boards acknowledged that "complete prevention is practically infeasible." This recognition reduced blame and fostered a sense of psychological safety, enabling CISOs to concentrate on containment, communication, and recovery. Therefore, boards should be educated that complete prevention is practically infeasible. Shifting the board's focus to response readiness fosters the psychological safety needed for a CISO to prioritize containment over blame-shifting.

Participants highlighted the challenges faced by policymakers and regulators due to cross-jurisdictional requirements and the tension between conducting thorough forensic investigations and meeting tight notification deadlines. These pressures underscore the need to harmonize notification rules more effectively and to establish timelines that realistically reflect the complexities of investigations. CISOs described operating within a narrow corridor: underreporting risks penalties, while overreporting invites increased scrutiny. Policymakers should recognize the temporal distortion identified in the first 72 hours of a breach. Rigid notification windows may incentivize "under-reporting" or "over-reporting," both of which invite scrutiny. Therefore, this study advocates for materiality-based reporting and regulatory safe harbors for good-faith disclosures made during this window to help alleviate this dilemma. Finally, CISOs observed that customers and investors interpret breaches through different lenses and seek different information. Standardized disclosures may fail to meet these needs. Therefore organizations should move beyond standardized disclosures to develop tailored communication templates. These should address the "locus of causality" for customers while monitoring "social media trends" for investors, reflecting the divergent ways different stakeholders interpret breach data. Table III synthesizes the practical implications of this study across five key stakeholder groups, providing actionable recommendations grounded in the lived experiences of CISOs during breach response. These implications translate the phenomenological findings into concrete organizational strategies, leadership development priorities, governance reforms, and research directions.

TABLE III: SUMMARY OF PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Stakeholder Group	Key Implications	Actionable Recommendations
Organizations	Breach response requires crisis leadership competencies beyond technical expertise	Expand CISO recruitment criteria to include communication skills, ethical decision-making, and psychological resilience
	Psychological strain undermines decision quality	Develop technical playbooks with pre-approved legal language and communication templates
	Pre-breach preparation determines response effectiveness	Integrate mental health resources into incident response plans (team rotation, digital detox protocols, psychological support)
		Establish clear escalation protocols and stakeholder notification procedures
CISOs & Security	Role transforms from technical expert to	Transition to <i>resilience leadership</i> model integrating mental

Leaders	<i>organizational sense-maker and governance pivot</i>	health support alongside forensic analysis
	First 48-72 hours represent distinct phenomenological crucible	Develop tolerance for epistemic ambiguity and procedural frameworks as psychological anchors
	<i>Satisficing under scrutiny</i> is realistic strategy, not failure	Create stakeholder-specific communication templates (customers: locus of causality; investors: social media monitoring)
		Prioritize team well-being as core IR competency
Boards & Executives	Complete breach prevention is practically infeasible	Shift governance focus from prevention metrics to response preparedness indicators
	Realistic expectations reduce blame culture and enable psychological safety	Acknowledge breach likelihood to create psychological safety for candid reporting
	Response readiness more critical than prevention promises	Educate boards on satisficing vs. optimization during crisis
		Support mental health resources as operational necessity, not optional benefit
Regulators & Policymakers	Cross-jurisdictional requirements create competing pressures	Harmonize international notification requirements to reduce jurisdictional conflicts
	Notification timelines may not reflect forensic investigation realities	Establish materiality-based reporting frameworks reflecting investigation complexity
	Under-reporting and over-reporting both carry risks	Create regulatory safe harbors for good-faith disclosures made within first 72 hours
		Design timeline provisions acknowledging temporal distortion of early breach response
Researchers	Phenomenological approaches reveal dimensions missed by technical/outcome-focused studies	Investigate "career crucible" effect: does surviving breach build credential or create permanent reputational stain?
	Breach response is fundamentally sociotechnical phenomenon	Conduct longitudinal studies on cumulative toll of repeated breach leadership
	Long-term career impacts remain unexplored	Develop integrative frameworks modeling interdependencies between technical response, emotional regulation, and stakeholder interpretation
		Treat psychological factors as first-order variables, not peripheral concerns

I. Limitations

While this study provides valuable phenomenological insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the sample was limited to CISOs in the U.S. and Canada, which may not reflect experiences in other regulatory and cultural contexts. Second, retrospective accounts may be subject to memory bias, though member checking helped mitigate this concern. Third, participants who agreed to interviews may represent those more comfortable discussing their experiences, potentially excluding the voices of CISOs who experienced more severe psychological consequences. Fourth, the study focused on the period from detection through early recovery; future research should explicitly investigate the public breach as a "career crucible" that can either build or destroy a leader's long-term professional marketability. Participants described accountability as an "ultimate loss of control" and a "public trial," yet the long-term impacts on their career trajectories and professional standing remain unmapped. Future inquiry should determine if surviving the "face of failure" serves as a credential of resilience or a permanent reputational stain in the executive labor market. Finally, the cumulative toll of serving as a public face of failure may increase vulnerability to burnout over a career, necessitating longitudinal studies on CISO well-being.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This phenomenological study sheds light on the experiences of CISOs during the critical period from breach detection to public disclosure and early recovery. The findings reveal that breach response is not merely a technical event but a profound leadership challenge. CISOs reported abrupt role transitions, persistent uncertainty, and a reliance on procedural frameworks to facilitate decision-making. They navigated competing demands—technical, legal, reputational, and operational—through compromise rather than striving for perfection. Ethical judgment remained constant while psychological toll proved significant. Communication was also central: CISOs needed to translate evolving information for executives and boards, reassure customers, respond to regulators, and withstand external scrutiny.

The study advances theory by providing a phenomenological foundation for understanding leadership during cybersecurity crises. It highlights dimensions often overlooked in research focused on technical processes, organizational outcomes, or survey-based stress measures. These insights also have practical significance. The study makes a compelling case that effective breach response depends on more than playbooks and tools; it requires support for both the leader's and the team's well-being. An ethical culture guides difficult decisions, informs boards with realistic expectations, and fosters thorough preparation that reduces cognitive load when pressure is at its peak. Across the accounts of 16 CISOs, one message stands out: breach response extends beyond problem-solving. It demands stewardship and resilience. As threats intensify and regulatory demands increase, the human side of breach leadership becomes essential—not optional—for recovery and the survival of the organization. Future research should prioritize the "career crucible" effect, examining factors that protect or undermine CISO effectiveness over time, and how the long-term impact of repeated breaches influences professional marketability and psychological resilience.

About the Author

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